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TIB

Preservation Planning: Monitoring the risk of file format obsolescence in TIBs AV holdings

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London, 24. October 2018
No Time to Wait! Rough Consensus and Running Archives

Agenda

1. **Obsolescence**
2. **Normalization – yes or no?**
3. **OAIS – Preservation Planning**
4. **Monitor the Risk of Obsolescence**
 - **View Paths**
5. **Migration**

References

“the phenomenon that occurs when information stored in a particular file format is no longer accessible using current technology.”
Ryan 2014, p. 2.

“Obsolescence describes a state of becoming obsolete, rather than a state of already being obsolete.”
Pearson and Webb 2008, p. 93.

*file format that is **at risk** to become
inaccessible by our **designated**
community*

Normalization

Amount	Container	Video-Codec	Audio-Codec
7384	MPEG-4	AVC	AAC, Version 4
1062	WebM, Format : WebM	VP8	Vorbis
963	MPEG-PS	MPEG Video, Version 2	MPEG Audio, Version 1
765	MPEG-4	AVC	AAC
706	MPEG-PS	MPEG Video, Version 1	MPEG Audio, Version 1
557	MPEG-4	MPEG-4 Visual	AAC, Version 4
421	MPEG-4	MPEG-4 Visual	
210	WebM, Version 2	VP8	Vorbis
175	MPEG-TS	AVC	AC-3
97	MPEG-PS	MPEG Video, Version 2	
93	AVI	AVC	PCM
46	MPEG-PS	MPEG Video, Version 2	AC-3, Format : DVD-Video
44	Flash Video	VP6	MPEG Audio, Version 1
37	MPEG-PS	MPEG Video, Version 2	MPEG Audio, Version 1, Format : MPEG Audio, Version 1, Format : RLE
33	Flash Video	VP6	MPEG Audio, Version 2
31	MPEG-4	AVC	
22	MPEG-PS	MPEG Video, Version 2	MPEG Audio, Version 1, Format : DVD-Video
30	MPEG-4	MPEG-4 Visual	AAC
...

Normalization

Advantages

Limited set of formats in the archive

- validation
- preservation planning
- less tools

Disadvantages

- migration necessary by producer
 - undocumented changes of material
 - delivering material is unattractive
- or migration necessary by archive
 - work load
 - keeping original (authenticity!) -> more storage space needed

**Sometimes we have to take everything we can get
... just the way it is**

OAIS – Preservation Planning

Figure 4-1: OAIS Functional Entities

Watch

Technology Watch

Community Watch

Preservation Watch

Monitor the Risk of Obsolescence

Indicators for Obsolescence:

Ryan (2014): Who’s afraid of file format obsolescence?

- conducted and evaluated expert interviews
- compared 21 indicators

*“the only factor that can be considered a direct cause to file format endangerment is **rendering software available**. Secondary factors to this are **specifications available** and **community/3rd party support**”*

Ryan (2014), p.210

View Paths

View paths for the majority of file formats in TIBs AV holdings

Format	View Path
Container: MPEG-4 Video: AVC Audio: AAC, Version 4	Intel® Core™ i7-8700 – Windows 10 – Windows Media Player Version 12 <hr/> Intel® Core™ i5-3470 – Windows 8.1 Pro – VLC Media Player Version 2.2.2
Container: WebM Video: VP8 Audio: Vorbis	Intel® Core™ i7-8700 – Windows 10 – MPC-HC Version 1.7.13 <hr/> Intel® Core™ i5-3470 – Windows 8.1 Pro – VLC Media Player Version 2.2.2
Container: MPEG-PS Video: MPEG Video, Version 2 Audio: MPEG Audio, Version 1	Intel® Core™ i7-8700 – Windows 10 – Windows Media Player Version 12 <hr/> Intel® Core™ i5-3470 – Windows 8.1 Pro – VLC Media Player Version 2.2.2

Concept View Paths: Steenbakkens, Johan F. (2005): Digital Archiving in the Twenty-First Century: Practice at the National Library of the Netherlands

View Paths

🏠 / Preservation: Formats / Details

Name	ExL-Fmt-161	Created on	
Description	WebM	Created by	
Classification	Video		

General Details Related Applications Risk Ident

	Name ▾	Description
1	✓ ExL-App-1	MPC-HC (64-bit)

🏠 / Preservation: Applications / Details

Name	ExL-App-1	Created on	22/10/2018	Updated on	22/10/2018
Description	MPC-HC (64-bit)	Created by	Ex Libris	Updated by	Merle Friedrichsen

General Details Related Formats Sustainability Factors Notes History

Name	ExL-App-1
Description	MPC-HC (64-bit)
Version	1.7.13
License Type	Open Source
Registry Type	EX Global
Registry ID	-
Service Pack Level	-
Vendor Name	-
Support end Date	-
Role List	-
Deployment	-
Alias	-
Family	-
Default File Format	-

Local Fields ▾

hardware platform Intel (R) Core (TM) i7-8700 - Windows 10

Field Description Hardware Platform on which the software runs, CPU

Outlook - Migration

Migrate to a suitable format

According to Todd, Malcolm, 2009. File formats for preservation:
Technology Watch Report.

Outlook - Migration

Preservation Planning with Rosetta

- extract technical metadata upon ingest
- automated risk report (based on view paths)
- creating sets on the base of risk report (and additional technical metadata, collection, rights...)
- define evaluation criteria
- define tool for migration (internal or external)
- run test and analyse results (automated or manual)
- sign-off preservation plan (or refine)

Future work:

develop a migration plugin for our archival software (Rosetta) to migrate to ffv1 / mkv (with ffmpeg)

References

- Pearson, David; Webb, Colin (2008):** Defining File Format Obsolescence: A Risky Journey. In *IJDC* 3 (1), pp. 89–106. DOI: [10.2218/ijdc.v3i1.44](https://doi.org/10.2218/ijdc.v3i1.44).
- Recommended Practice CCSDS 650.0-M-2, June 2012:** Reference Model for an Open Archival Information System (OAIS). Available online at <https://public.ccsds.org/pubs/650x0m2.pdf>.
- Ryan, Heather M. (2014):** Who's afraid of File Format Obsolescence? Evaluating File Format Endangerment Levels and Factors for the Creation of a File Format Endangerment Index. University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill. School of Information and Library Science. Available online at <https://cdr.lib.unc.edu/record/uuid:86e05605-97e3-40de-927a-ce5f5a6fa4d0>.
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- Todd, Malcolm (2009):** File formats for preservation. Technology Watch Report. Available online at https://www.dpconline.org/component/docman/?task=doc_download&gid=375.

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